

The Evolution of Management and Marketing in the Digital Era

José Daniel Barquero
ESERP Business & Law School

Jaume Llopis
University of Navarra IESE Business School

Received September 27, 2019; accepted October 29, 2019.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the evolution, and changes in the styles of direction of the organizations since the beginning of management in the 20th century till now, through a review of academic literature, and existing research about management. From a set of interviews to executives of European corporations, following parameters found in academic literature, a deep change in the priorities of senior management is observed. Recent changes in the managerial focus and in the new social context are analyzed. New tools of digital marketing are enumerated, and a new academic model of public relations based on persuasion is proposed, for the success of campaigns.

KEYWORDS

Changes, leadership, management, marketing, digitization, public relations.

Senge, P. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. Doubleday/Currency, New York.

Tannenbaum, R.; Weschler, I. R. and Massarik, F. (1961). *Leadership Organization: A Behavioural Approach*, McGraw-Hill, New York.

Taylor, F. W. (1911). *The Principles of Scientific Management*. Harper & Brothers, New York.

Weber, M. (1947). *The Theory of Social and Economic Organizations*. Oxford University Press, New York.

Williamson, O.E. (1975). *Markets and Hierarchies: Analysis and Antitrust Implications*, Free Press, New York.